

THERMAL FATIGUE OF INTERPENETRATING C/AL COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: We produced interpenetrating graphite/aluminium composites by pressure infiltration of aluminium-silicon alloys into microporous graphite preforms. Infiltration with the AlSi7Ba alloy significantly increases the flexural strength and fracture toughness of the composites, resulting in values of up to 120 MPa and 1.93 MPam^{1/2}, respectively. After thermal cycling, a slight reduction in the mechanical properties for graphite/AlSi7Ba composites is observed, mainly due to precipitation reactions and silicon phase coarsening. No deterioration of mechanical properties is measured for graphite/AlSi12 composites. Due to the large mismatch in the coefficients of thermal expansion of the constituent phases, stress relaxation processes in combination with an increase in the sample's length occurred after thermal cycling. We show that the electrical conductivity is highly sensitive to damage evolution within the metallic phase. Independent of the infiltrated alloy, void formation in the highly conducting metal phase causes electrical conductivity to deteriorate after thermal cycling.

KEYWORDS: Interpenetrating phase composites, liquid metal infiltration, thermal fatigue, thermomechanical properties, X-ray tomography, aluminium, porous preform, graphite.

INTRODUCTION

Multiphase materials in which each phase is three-dimensionally interconnected throughout the structure make possible the development of materials with multifunctional characteristics [1]. In this study, graphite/aluminium composites (C/Al) with an interpenetrating network structure were produced by pressure infiltration of aluminium alloys with varying silicon contents into isotropic microporous graphite preforms with an open porosity of about 15 vol.%. The principle of the infiltration of porous graphites with light metals is to force the liquid melt into the preform under external pressure to overcome the bad wettability between aluminium and graphite.

Due to their specific properties, light-metal-infiltrated graphites are attractive for use in lightweight components such as internal combustion engine parts. Here the low coefficient of thermal expansion and the temperature resistance of carbon materials, in addition to low density, represent significant advantages compared to conventional monolithic Al alloys. And to fulfil the mechanical requirements of the automotive industry for piston materials, the metal reinforcement of porous graphite is a necessity.

For different ceramic/metal composite systems the incorporation of a ductile metal phase is known to improve mechanical properties as compared to those of monolithic ceramic

preforms. The main strengthening/toughening mechanism assumed to be effective in reinforced ceramics is the plastic stretching of the ductile metallic phase [2,3]. This bridging mechanism can be even more effective in conjunction with residual compressive stresses in the ceramic phase, induced by thermal expansion mismatch between the constituent phases [4]. Nevertheless, due to the large difference in the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) between graphite and aluminium, thermal fatigue may cause mechanical and physical properties to deteriorate.

In this study we used the indirect squeeze casting method to fabricate interpenetrating C/Al composites. The mechanical and physical properties of porous graphite preforms and of composites infiltrated with AlSi7Ba or AlSi12 were measured at room temperature, in the as-produced condition and after thermal cycling (TC) treatment. We performed TC treatment to investigate the resistance of C/Al composites to thermal fatigue. Specimens were thermally cycled at between room temperature and 573 K for up to 1000 cycles.

EXPERIMENTAL

Monolithic materials

Isotropic polycrystalline porous graphites with an open porosity of about 15 vol.%, manufactured by Schunk Kohlenstofftechnik GmbH (Germany), were used as preforms. The graphite preforms were infiltrated either with AlSi7Ba (7 wt.% Si, 0.25 wt.% Ba) or eutectic AlSi12 (12 wt.% Si) alloy.

Indirect squeeze casting process

All graphite preforms with dimensions of 150x65x22 mm³ were infiltrated with a UBE HVSC 350 indirect squeeze casting machine at ARC in Ranshofen, Austria. The superheated aluminium melts (1023 K) were pressed into preheated graphite preforms (953 K) with a hydraulic plunger and solidified under a pressure of about 75 MPa.

Mechanical testing

To determine the flexural strength, 4-point bending tests at room temperature were performed on an Instron 8562 universal testing machine using a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. All bending test samples were 3x4x45 mm³ in size.

Fracture toughness tests at room temperature with porous graphite preforms and C/Al composites were performed according to the SEVNB method (single edge V-notched beam) [5], using 5 bars of each material of the same size as used for the flexural strength tests. With this method we produced notch tip radii of about 30 µm. The measurements were performed with a Zwick 1478 using a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min.

To investigate the susceptibility of the C/Al composites to thermal fatigue, the specimens were thermally cycled at between room temperature and 573 K with a modified Heraeus furnace. The thermal cycling was performed 1000 times using the pneumatic motion of a hollow sample holder. The samples were cooled to room temperature by exposure to cold air from a hair dryer, achieving a cooling rate of 5 K/s.

Determination of physical properties

To verify infiltration quality and experimental reproducibility, 4 samples of each material were tested. For all measurements, we used cylindrical samples with a diameter of 5 mm and a length of 30 mm.

Electrical resistivity at room temperature was measured using a 4-point direct current technique. All measurements were performed at a constant current of 1000 mA. Thermal expansion behaviour was measured from 298 K to 573 K by differential dilatometry, using a differential Bähr Dilatometer Dil 802S working in an air atmosphere. All measurements were performed at a heating and a cooling rate of 2.5 K/min.

X-ray microtomography measurements

The size of the microstructural features of the C/Al composites under consideration requires a tomographic resolution that can only be achieved by exploiting the high brilliance of a synchrotron-based X-ray beam. X-ray microtomography measurements were performed at the Materials Science Beamline of the Swiss Light Source (SLS) at the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI) in Villigen, Switzerland. All measurements were performed with a monochromatic beam energy of 10 keV with a corresponding flux density of 10^{14} photons/s. The individual 2-D tomograms were reconstructed by a filtered back-projection procedure. The resulting effective pixel size is 0.7 μm . A detailed description of the Material Science Beamline at SLS can be found in [6].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mechanical Properties

A typical microstructure of the C/AlSi7Ba composite is shown in Fig. 1. Here the bright phase corresponds to the metal. At this length scale, the composite looks homogeneous. However, at higher magnifications inhomogeneous regions can be detected, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1: Optical micrograph of interpenetrating C/AlSi7Ba composite.

Fig. 2: Uninfiltratable graphite agglomerate in C/AlSi7Ba composite.

Fig. 2 shows a graphite agglomerate (within the dashed line) that cannot be infiltrated. The size of such graphite agglomerates is directly related to mechanical properties. At higher magnifications the silicon phase in the Al-Si alloy became visible after etching the composites

for 5 s in Keller's reagent. As seen in Fig. 4, the microstructure of the metal phase is characterised by the formation of about 50 vol.% primary α -aluminium and 50 vol.% eutectic. Because of the short contact time between graphite and aluminium in the indirect squeeze casting process, it was possible to avoid the formation of hygroscopic aluminium carbide (Al_4C_3).

The flexural strength (σ_c) properties of the graphite preform and the corresponding composites measured at room temperature before and after thermal cycling are listed in Table 1. As seen from this table, C/Al composites exhibit a significantly greater flexural strength than the corresponding porous graphite preform.

Table 1: Flexural strength (σ_c) of porous graphite and graphite/aluminium (C/Al) composites measured at room temperature, before and after thermal cycling (TC).

	C preform	C / AlSi7Ba	C / AlSi12
σ_c before TC [MPa]	61 ± 2	122 ± 5	114 ± 6
σ_c after TC [MPa]	58 ± 4	113 ± 2	115 ± 9

The increase in flexural strength of about 60 MPa by metal infiltration cannot be explained by a strength contribution of the aluminium phase calculated according to a simple rule of mixtures. It is more appropriate to relate the strength increase to the enhanced fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) of interpenetrating C/Al composites [7,8], shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Fracture toughness of C/AlSi7Ba and C/AlSi12 composites before and after TC, with corresponding values for the porous graphite preform.

The flexural strength and fracture toughness of the composites increases by a factor of two compared to the porous graphite preform. Interpenetrating C/Al composites with even greater strength can be produced by reducing the critical flaw size of coarse graphite grains and/or by enhancing the metal content. Critical defects are already present in the graphite preform and cannot be eliminated by metal infiltration. Therefore, efforts in control of processing from the

synthesis of raw materials through forming and sintering are necessary to reduce the critical defect size. By employing such a specific preform modification (called preform C_m) the composite strength was even enhanced to 150 MPa (see Table 2).

From Fig. 3 it is clearly visible that thermal loading affects the fracture toughness of the C/AlSi7Ba composite. This effect is less apparent in the C/AlSi12 composite. As expected, the fracture toughness of the uninfiltrated graphite preform is not affected by TC treatment. The same tendency is observed for flexural strength. The C/AlSi7Ba composite shows a decrease in flexural strength of about 7%, whereas C/AlSi12 shows no significant influence by thermal loading. This behaviour can be explained by the microstructural effect of the metallic phase on fracture toughness. The decrease in mechanical properties in C/AlSi7Ba composite due to TC treatment is apparently caused by a modification of the metallic phase. Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 illustrate this.

Fig. 4: Silicon distribution in C/AlSi7Ba composite before thermal cycling.

Fig. 5: Silicon precipitation and coarsening in C/AlSi7Ba composite after thermal cycling.

Precipitation of silicon particles in α -Al and coarsening of the eutectic silicon phase during TC treatment are the most obvious effects of a decrease in mechanical properties after TC. However, stress relaxation processes and local debonding may also contribute.

It is worth mentioning that in contrast to C/AlSi7Ba composite no or much less α -aluminium is formed in the C/AlSi12 composite, and thus silicon is more homogeneously distributed. Consequently no silicon precipitation is observed in the C/AlSi12 composite after TC. The assumption concerning the correlation between precipitation reactions and decreases in fracture toughness and flexural strength, respectively, was confirmed by thermal cycling treatment of C_m /AlSi12.

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the C_m /AlSi12 composite measured before and after TC with modified preform C_m .

	σ_c [MPa]	Number of samples	Weibull modulus m
C_m /AlSi12 before TC	153 ± 7	25	27
C_m /AlSi12 after TC	153 ± 6	24	31

Up to now, the eutectic AlSi12 alloy is the most promising alloy for infiltration of this specific graphite preform by the indirect squeeze casting process.

Physical properties and microtomography

The relevant physical properties of monolithic phases and the corresponding composites determined before TC are listed in Table 3. Here the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) corresponds to a temperature-averaged CTE between 373 K and 573 K.

Table 3: Physical properties of monolithic phases and the corresponding composites determined before TC.

	CTE [$10^{-6}/\text{K}$]	σ_{el} [$10^6/\Omega\text{m}$]	λ [W/mK]
AlSi7Ba alloy	22.9 ± 0.5	26 ± 1	183 ± 3
C preform	6.3 ± 0.1	0.043 ± 0.001	49 ± 1
C/AlSi7Ba composite	9.1 ± 0.3	0.53 ± 0.03	75 ± 2

The CTE of interpenetrating C/Al composites is about 2 to 3 times lower than that of monolithic Al alloys. Due to the fact that the CTE of the graphite preform is almost 4 times lower than that of Al alloys, thermal fatigue can be a severe problem. The large mismatch in CTE between graphite and aluminium leads to the buildup of high stress levels in the composites during cooling after infiltration. These stresses can relax at least partially after a succeeding thermal treatment.

We observed such stress relaxation processes in the form of a “hysteresis” in dilatometer measurements, shown in Fig. 6. The arrows correspond to the heating and cooling cycles. The composite specimens show such hysteretic behaviour before thermal cycling only.

Fig. 6: Influence of TC on the expansion behaviour of C/AlSi7Ba composite.

As can be seen in Fig. 6, the hysteretic behaviour results in a residual length change. This change is not only recorded by dilatometry but can also be verified by micrometer measurements. The most significant length change is observed at the end of the first thermal cycle ($0.03 \pm 0.01\%$). During the next cycles less net residual length change is generated. After 1000 thermal cycles a total strain of $0.12 \pm 0.01\%$ is measured. After TC, the C/Al composite shows reversible temperature-strain behaviour without residual strain. The presence of positive residual strain at the end of the first thermal cycle is a feature often found

after the first dilatometer measurement. As already mentioned, open hystereses are probably the consequence of the reduction of residual stresses due to relaxation effects [9].

Thermal cycling treatment and the resulting relaxation effects may also affect other physical properties negatively. An indication of material damage due to thermal cycling was observed by measuring electrical conductivity (σ_{el}). Fig. 7 illustrates the significant increase in the electrical conductivity of composites by aluminium infiltration, in comparison to the porous graphite preform. Differences in electrical conductivity of C/Al composites before thermal cycling most likely occur because of small differences in metal content.

Due to greater electrical conductivity in the metallic phase by more than two orders of magnitude compared to the graphite preform, the decrease in electrical conductivity after thermal cycling can be attributed to damage evolution in the metallic phase.

Fig. 7: Influence of thermal cycling on electrical conductivity.

It is important to note that in contrast to mechanical properties, where the decrease in fracture toughness due to thermal cycling depends on the aluminium alloy composition, the decrease in electrical conductivity is independent of the infiltrated alloy. Therefore the decrease in electrical conductivity cannot be attributed to precipitation reactions and/or phase modification of the silicon phase. It is worth mentioning that TC treatment of monolithic AlSi7Ba and AlSi12 even lead to an increase in electrical conductivity.

The decrease in electrical conductivity due to thermal cycling is attributed to damage of the metallic phase. Although damage evolution in the graphite preform is a realistic hypothesis, this makes no decisive contribution to the significant decrease. Local debonding along the C/Al interface was observed by preparing a lamella for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a focused ion beam (FIB) microscope. But even if the composite completely debonded, the electrical phase contrast ($\sigma_{el}(Al)/\sigma_{el}(C)$) between aluminium and graphite is so high (about 600) that the metallic phase is still the dominant carrier of the electrical current. Therefore, lower conductivity after TC can be explained by damage evolution within the metallic phase.

Synchrotron radiation-based X-ray tomographic microscopy (XTM) revealed void formation within the metallic phase after TC. The C/AlSi7Ba composite in Fig. 8 shows small black points inside the bright aluminium phase. Here these black regions indicate a lack of material. The images correspond to consecutive equidistant tomogram slices from the C/AlSi7Ba composite after TC. The vertical distance between the tomogram slice a and tomogram slice j is $6.3 \mu m$ ($9 \times 0.7 \mu m$).

Fig. 8: Adjacent tomogram slices of C/AlSi7Ba composite after TC, showing void formation within the encircled region in the aluminium phase.

Based on these tomogram slices we conclude that thermal cycling led to void formation in the metallic phase of thermally-cycled C/Al composites. Due to these defects, the effective cross-section of aluminium ligaments is locally reduced. That is probably one reason for a decrease in electrical conductivity. Void formation and growth were also identified as the predominant damage mechanisms in carbon fibre reinforced copper composites, relaxing the internal stresses during thermal cycling [10]. A decrease in stiffness and density with thermal cycling in the alumina fibre/magnesium alloy composite was attributed to void formation at the reinforcement/matrix interface [11].

Other possible damage mechanisms may be the breakage of thin Al ligaments and/or the formation and growth of micro-cracks during thermal cycling. Both would contribute to a decrease in electrical conductivity.

CONCLUSIONS

Interpenetrating phase composites were produced by means of an indirect squeeze casting process. Porous graphite preforms with an open porosity of about 15 vol.% were infiltrated with AlSi7Ba or a eutectic AlSi12 alloy. We have shown that the light-metal infiltration leads to a significant increase in the composite's strength compared to that of a porous graphite preform. We conclude that the increase in fracture toughness is due to the small addition of a ductile metal phase. Thermal cycling experiments indicated that mechanical properties can be sensitive to thermal loading, depending on the infiltrated aluminium alloy. The decrease in fracture toughness due to thermal cycling is mainly attributed to aging. So far, the eutectic AlSi12 alloy is the most promising alloy for the indirect squeeze casting process.

Due to differences in the coefficients of thermal expansion between aluminium and graphite, residual stresses are built up after cooling from the infiltration temperature. It is worth mentioning that during thermal cycling, stress relaxation is accompanied by dimensional instability of the composites during the first few cycles (length increase). It has been shown that the electrical conductivity is very sensitive to thermal fatigue. The decrease in electrical conductivity is independent of the infiltrated alloy and can be attributed to damage evolution in the metallic phase. Using powerful synchrotron-based X-ray microtomography, void formation within the aluminium phase could be visualised in consecutive tomogram slices.

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